

FAILURE STRAIN ENHANCEMENT

IN CARBON/GLASS FIBRE HYBRID COMPOSITES

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1. INTRODUCTION

Hybrid fibre-composites, consisting of two, or more, fibre types embedded in a common resin matrix have recently attracted considerable attention, see Phillips [1], since they offer the possibility of achieving a balance of mechanical properties that cannot be realised in composites of one fibre type. Amongst the possibilities claimed for hybrid composites are the more cost effective utilisation of expensive reinforcing fibres such as carbon, and a modification of the mode of failure from the often sudden and catastrophic sequence observed in many all-carbon composites, to a more gradual and controlled mode where one fibre continues to carry stress after failure has initiated in the other.

Typically a high modulus fibre with a low strain to failure is combined with one of lower modulus but higher failure strain, e.g. carbon with glass. Bunsell and Harris [2] tested three layer glass-carbon hybrids and reported that the failure strain for high-modulus carbon was increased by 80% in the glass-carbon sandwich compared with that for an all carbon-fibre composite. However, their all-carbon composite showed an unusually low strain at failure of only 0.3%. They were able to account for some 10% of the observed increase in the hybrid by the residual compressive stress induced in the carbon layer, due to the thermal expansion mismatch between the glass and carbon-fibres, when the material was cooled down from its moulding temperature. Aveston and Sillwood [3] made hybrids by incorporating separated carbon-fibre tows with glass so that the individual carbon-fibres were highly dispersed with respect to the glass. They found up to 100% increase in the carbon-fibre failure strain. Their results are, however, hardly comparable with those of Bunsell and Harris since the latter used a thick (0.4mm) carbon ply thickness. Zweben [4], dispersed tows of carbon-fibre (Thornel 300) with polyaramid (Kevlar^R 49) but found a failure strain enhancement of only 4% in the carbon.

In the present work we have attempted to explore the effects of the state of dispersion and the fibre ratio on the failure strain enhancement, and have studied the modes of failure observed in simple sandwich laminate hybrid composites.

NOMENCLATURE

Symbols

CT	High tensile carbon fibre composite
CM	High modulus carbon fibre composite
EG	"E" - glass fibre composite
P	Proportion of hybrid thickness represented by each reinforcing component (subscripted)
t	Thickness of a hybrid component (subscripted)
D	Dispersion
ϵ	Strain of hybrid or hybrid component (subscripted)
T	Temperature
α	Composite thermal expansion coefficient (subscripted)
S	Stiffness of hybrid or hybrid component (subscripted)
γ_D	Debonding fracture energy
γ_T	Transverse fracture energy
τ	Frictional force per unit area at debonded interface
x	Distance (along specimen axis) from carbon-ply failure
β	$\left(\frac{1}{S_g} + \frac{1}{S_c} \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}}$
L_D	Debond length to one side of carbon-ply fracture
W	Energy term

Subscripts

c	Carbon-ply
g	Glass-ply
h	Hybrid
u	Ultimate tensile
r	Smallest representative repeat (thickness)
t	Thermal

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

All the composites were fabricated from unidirectional fibre "pre-preg" sheets. The fibre types were surface treated high-modulus carbon (CM), surface treated high-strength carbon (CT), and E-glass (EG). The impregnating resin was a proprietary epoxide system (Fothergill and Harvey Ltd., Code 69). The pre-preg sheets were designed to give a lamina thickness of 0.125mm at 0.6 volume fraction. The nominal mechanical properties of the fibres as derived from composite tests are given in Table I.

TABLE I
Mechanical Properties of Fibres (Typical)

Fibre Type	Tensile Modulus GPa	Tensile Strength GPa	Failure Strain
CM	320	2.22	0.0069
CT	240	2.76	0.0115
EG	73	2.02	0.0276

2.2 Fabrication

Laminates were prepared by laying up the appropriate sequence of

100 x 200mm sheets of pre-preg (fibres parallel to 200mm dimension), in an open-ended trough mould, and pressing between the heated platens of a hand-operated screw press. The pre-preg pack was pre-heated in the press under minimal pressure for 10 minutes at 130°C to melt the resin. It was then removed to a vacuum oven and degassed for 15 minutes at 130°C when it was returned to the press. The platen temperature was then raised to 175°C over a period of 10 minutes whilst the press was gently screwed down onto metal stops which established the final laminate thickness. In this way the excess resin and any remaining voids were expelled through the open ends of the trough mould and good quality laminates produced. The cure was continued at 175°C for 60 minutes after which the mould was removed from the press, the laminate extracted and finally post-cured for a further 3 hours at 175°C.

Parallel sided tensile test pieces 200mm x 10mm wide were cut from the laminates with a diamond saw and aluminium alloy and tabs bonded on with an epoxy resin adhesive. Strain gauges were positioned on the central portion of the gauge length as shown in Figure 1.

2.3 Testing

At least five test pieces of each lay-up were tested in an Instron testing machine at a strain rate of $\approx 1.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The tests were monitored with an acoustic emission detector which measured count rate. Both load-strain and acoustic rate were autographically recorded, a typical trace being shown in Figure 2. After fracture the general failure pattern was noted and specimens were taken from typical regions for optical and scanning electron microscopy.

Fig. 1. Construction of standard specimen.

Fig. 2. Load-strain, and acoustic emission rate-strain traces for a hybrid showing successive fractures of the carbon-ply at a,b, and c.

2.4 Range of Composites Tested

The aim of the work was to investigate the effect of hybrid ratio and the state of dispersion of the two fibre types. This has been done within the restrictions imposed by the choice of a pre-preg system which allows only for a through thickness variation in dispersion of the laminate, and variations in quanta of one pre-preg layer.

Most of the work was done on glass-carbon-glass sandwich laminates using both CM and CT carbon, but some multiple-layer-laminates were also prepared. Details of laminate geometry together with basic mechanical test data are given in Table II.

When comparing the properties of hybrid composites two fundamental constitutional parameters should be considered, the hybrid ratio and the state of dispersion.

The hybrid ratio is expressed here as the proportions of the total laminate thickness represented by each reinforcing component. (e.g. for a 1:1:1 glass-carbon-glass hybrid the carbon fraction, $P_C = 0.33$, and the glass fraction, $P_g = 0.67$.) We have defined dispersion as the reciprocal of the thickness (in metres) of the smallest representative repeat unit of the laminate:

$$D = \frac{1}{t_r}$$

In the case of the simple sandwich laminates t_r is the total laminate thickness.

Figure 3 is a two-dimensional representation of the range of laminates studied. The left-hand vertical axes show dispersion, and the number of pre-preg laminae in the thickness respectively, whilst the horizontal axis is the carbon fraction, P_C . The two sets of hyperbolae illustrate the restrictions that all laminates be constructed from integral numbers of laminae, and that for a balanced three-layer construction there must be an even number of glass laminae. Laminate geometrics satisfying these conditions are found at the intersections of the hyperbolae, and those fabricated are indicated. The open circles represent multiple-layer-laminates.

3. MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

Mechanical testing has shown that laminate geometry has a profound effect on the properties of the hybrids. The most notable is an increase in carbon layer failure strain of up to 35% (CT) or 45% (CM), and this is termed the "hybrid effect". Further important findings are a size effect in all-carbon composites, and the observation of a multiple fracture failure mode, in which progressive failure occurs in the carbon component of the hybrid.

3.1 Observations Preceding Carbon-Ply Failure

The first portion of the load-strain curve is virtually linear and the observed elastic modulus is in close agreement with that predicted by the parallel rule of mixtures. Although no external changes are noted in this region, the acoustic emission rate count becomes significant at strains of about 0.005 and then increases progressively up to the first carbon ply failure, Figure 2. Microstructural examination of specimens loaded to just below the first carbon-ply

(a)

(b)

Fig. 3. The range of dispersion and carbon fraction covered by composites based on (a) high tensile carbon, (b) high modulus carbon.

Open circles represent multiple-layer laminates. The hyperbolae indicate the number of laminae in the component plies.

Fig. 4. Longitudinal section of a matrix crack limited in extent by glass fibres. Scale bar 10 μ m

Fig. 5. Matrix crack surrounding a carbon fibre at a resin-rich glass/carbon-ply interface.

(a) Surface reflection (b) Focus below surface showing crack arrest near adjacent fibres. Scale bar 10 μ m

failure strain typically shows few fibre breaks, but extensive matrix cracking. The matrix cracks are normal to the fibre axes (this was also the tension axis), and are clearly seen to have been arrested at the fibres, Figures 4 and 5. These matrix cracks appear to be more common in resin rich regions.

In an attempt to identify broken fibres, we have developed an electrolytic etching technique [11], which is able to distinguish between conducting and non-conducting fibres running through a thin ($\sim 0.1\text{mm}$) transverse section of the laminate. There is a colour change on conducting fibres, whereas unetched (broken) fibres remain bright, and are seen to be grouped, and frequently associated with matrix cracking, which appears bright under crossed polars (Figure 6). Up to fracture the number of isolated fibre breaks is small, about 10^{10} m^{-3} , and they have not been observed in longitudinal sections. It is probable that both fibre fractures and matrix cracks contribute to the build-up in acoustic emission observed, but it has not been possible to attribute their relative contributions.

3.2 Carbon-Ply Failure

On loading the hybrid laminate the near-linear load strain characteristic is maintained until a major failure occurs in the carbon-ply (Figure 2). At this point there is a transverse fracture across the carbon-ply with consequent debonding along the carbon-glass interface. The load-strain trace shows a load drop at this point but on further extension, the load rises, though at reduced slope. The exact shape of the curve is determined by the machine stiffness and by the position of the strain gauge relative to the position of the carbon-ply fracture. A high and irregular rate of acoustic emission is observed during the sequence of carbon ply failure and associated events.

Fig. 6. Etched cross section of failed hybrid showing: (a) Grouping of broken carbon fibres (bright unetched small fibres)

(b) Association of matrix cracks (bright areas) with carbon fibre breaks in the same field. (Polarized light). Scale bar $100\mu\text{m}$

Fig. 7. The hybrid and size effects plotted against carbon fraction and dispersion (logarithmic axis) for laminates based on (a) high tensile carbon, (b) high

modulus carbon. The contribution of thermal strains to the increased failure strain is indicated by solid bar.

TABLE II
LAMINATE PROPERTIES

Lay-up sequence No. of laminae of glass, carbon, glass	Dispersion (m^{-1}) $\times 10^3$	Carbon fraction P_c	Modulus (G Pa)	Failure stress (G Pa)	Failure strain	Debond length L_D (mm)	Hybrid Effect/ Size Effect. Carbon-ply failure strain increase, (%)
<u>E - Class composites</u>							
3 - -	2.67	0.0	45	1.20	.027	-	-
12 - -	0.67	0.0	44	1.21	.028	-	-
<u>High Tensile carbon: All-carbon composites and hybrids</u>							
- 1 -	8.00	1.0	126	0.97	.0077	-	-33
- 2 -	4.00	1.0	128	1.13	.0088	-	-24
- 3 -	2.67	1.0	143	1.48	.0103	-	-10
- 4 -	2.00	1.0	129	1.25	.0097	-	-16
- 12 -	0.67	1.0	144	1.66	.0115	-	0.0
1 1 1	2.67	0.33	83	1.04	.0125	32	+8.7
2 1 2	1.60	0.20	65	0.92	.0142	31	+24
3 1 3	1.14	0.14	59	0.87	.0148	17	+29
4 1 4	0.89	0.11	60	0.90	.0149	10	+30
6 1 6	0.62	0.08	55	0.82	.0150	6	+30
9 1 9	0.42	0.05	49	0.76	.0155	3	+35
2 2 2	1.33	0.33	76	1.03	.0135	>100	+17
3 2 3	1.00	0.25	72	0.97	.0135	>100	+17
1 3 1	1.60	0.60	104	1.43	.0137	100	+19
3 3 3	0.89	0.33	77	1.04	.0136	>100	+18
8 3 8	0.42	0.16	58	0.82	.0141	>100	+23
3 8 3	0.57	0.57	102	1.38	.0136	>100	+18
1 9 1	0.73	0.82	109	1.40	.0129	>100	+12
8 9 8	0.32	0.36	81	1.03	.0127	>100	+10
(1EG, 1CT) x 6	4.00	0.50	93	1.20	.0129	-	+12
(2EG, 2CT) x 3	2.00	0.50	90	1.23	.0136	-	+18
<u>High Modulus carbon: All-carbon composites and hybrids</u>							
- 3 -	2.67	1.0	184	1.11	.0060	-	-13
- 12 -	0.67	1.0	192	1.33	.0069	-	0.0
1 1 1	2.67	0.33	95	0.75	.0079	-	+15
2 2 2	1.33	0.33	99	0.83	.0084	-	+22
3 3 3	0.89	0.33	89	0.75	.0084	-	+22
6 7 6	0.42	0.37	100	0.82	.0082	-	+19
8 3 8	0.42	0.16	65	0.55	.0084	-	+22
9 1 9	0.42	0.05	50	0.51	.0101	-	+46
(1EG, 1CM) x 4	4.00	0.50	119	0.95	.0080	-	+16
(2EG, 2CM) x 2	2.00	0.50	119	0.87	.0073	-	+6

The strain at which the first carbon-ply failure occurred was found to be dependent on laminate geometry. The details are given in Table II, and in Figure 7. The hybrid effect (relative to a standard 1.5mm thick all-carbon laminate) is shown in a 3-dimensional representation against carbon-fraction and dispersion. It will be seen that the effect increases strongly as the carbon fraction is decreased and also increases as the dispersion is increased. Note also the reduced failure strain for the thinner all-carbon laminates. Part of the hybrid effect may be explained by the thermal stresses induced in the laminate (section 4.1) and this is also indicated on the diagrams. The effect is more pronounced in the case of the EG-CM hybrids.

Figure 8 shows the general characteristics of the region around the carbon-ply fracture. The main transverse fracture is typically of cruciform shape and debonding occurs between the carbon and glass plies outwards from the line where the transverse fracture intersects the glass-carbon interface. Note that the region between the two arms of the fracture is not debonded. This is clear from the photomicrographs of Figures 9 and 10. Figure 11 is a section cut in the plane of lamination and shows the irregular branched form of the fracture. We interpret this evidence to indicate that the fracture was initiated within the carbon-ply and that the cruciform cracks then grew out across the ply to the glass-carbon interface, which then debonded under the influence of the induced shear stresses. There is also a suggestion, Figure 11, that the fracture path propagated in one direction across the width of the test piece as evidenced by the direction of the branching.

Fig.8. Schematic of typical cruciform crack in the carbon-ply and associated debonding. The tensile axis is vertical.

Fig.9. Typical carbon ply failure showing the cruciform transverse fracture at centre, and interface debonding indicated by arrows.

3.3 Multiple Cracking

The measured range of debond lengths is rather large, from several millimetres to greater than 100mm (i.e. greater than the gauge length). In this latter case continued loading of the completely debonded specimen after the carbon ply failure results only in failure of the remaining glass plies at their ultimate strength, and the carbon has no further influence on the load carrying capacity of the laminate. When the debond length is less than the gauge length, further straining after the initial failure causes further fractures at random positions in the remaining bonded portions of the specimen. Repeated carbon ply failure at approximately constant load is shown in Figure 2, and is seen to be accompanied by high acoustic output. (In a multiply-cracked specimen the strain is not uniform along the gauge length, which accounts for the mismatch in the traces in Figure 2, as the A.E. trace was related to cross head displacement and the load trace to strain gauge reading.) Ultimately most of the hybrid becomes debonded, and the strength and stiffness approach that of the glass plies alone. As noted previously, there is a load drop associated with each carbon-ply fracture. On further straining the debonded zone has been observed to propagate, ultimately reaching a value which appears to be a characteristic of the particular hybrid geometry.

The practical significance of these observations is that the initial fracture in the carbon-ply does not propagate across the glass plies but is contained by the debonding at the carbon-glass interface. This debonded zone is also restricted and this implies that load can be progressively diffused back into carbon-ply away from the fracture so that the carbon-ply, away from the fracture zone, remains capable of bearing load. This will have a significant effect on the overall work of fracture, although this aspect has not been investigated in the present work.

Fig. 10. Scanning electron micrograph of a glass-ply after fracture and debonding of the carbon-ply. Short lengths of carbon fibre remain bonded as a result of the cruciform fracture, and delineate the fracture path.

DIRECTION OF FRACTURE →

500 μm

Fig. 11. Section of carbon-ply failure in the plane of lamination. Branching of the crack path suggest a direction of fracture as arrowed.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1 Thermal Contribution to Hybrid Effect

Carbon fibre has a small negative longitudinal thermal expansion coefficient, whereas glass fibre has a much larger positive coefficient, so on cooling from the resin-cure temperature the carbon component of a hybrid is placed in compression, and the glass in tension. The hybrid strain at carbon failure is expected to increase by an amount equal to the compressive strain in the carbon.

Figure 12 shows the thermally induced loads and strains in a hybrid after cooling (away from the regions of end effects) and is the model for thermal strain calculation. The thermal strain mismatch $\Delta\epsilon_t$, between carbon and glass plies, after cooling through a temperature difference ΔT is $\Delta\epsilon_t = (\alpha_c - \alpha_g) \Delta T$, where α_c and α_g are longitudinal expansion coefficients of the carbon and glass components. The fraction of this mismatch which appears as a strain in the carbon ply is $\frac{S_g}{S_h}$ where S_g and S_h are the glass component and hybrid stiffnesses respectively.

The carbon-ply compression is then $\epsilon_{ct} = \frac{S_g}{S_h} \Delta\epsilon_t$

The fraction $\frac{S_g}{S_h} = \frac{\epsilon_{ct}}{\Delta\epsilon_t}$ is a function only of material constants and

the hybrid ratio, and is independent of dispersion as seen in Figure 13 where it is plotted against P_c . The strain mismatch has also been measured experimentally by observation of the thermally induced bending of unbalanced laminates. This is 1.0×10^{-3} for the CT - EG system, and 0.93×10^{-3} for the CM - EG system.

Fig. 12. Thermal stress and strain in a sandwich hybrid after cure. The carbon-ply is in compression.

Fig. 13. The proportion of the thermally induced strain mismatch which is accommodation by compression in the carbon-ply, as a function of carbon fraction.

The proportion of the strain increase attributable to thermal contraction, shown in Figure 7, is only a small fraction of the total, and the thermal effect is therefore not a complete explanation of the observed phenomena.

4.2 Failure Theories

Failure in unidirectional composites may be considered in terms of either the statistical failure of fibres leading to some critical weakening of the composite [5-8], or by the application of linear elastic fracture mechanics, [9,10], assuming the material to be macroscopically homogeneous. The fracture mechanics approach is best suited to composites containing macroscopic flaws of known size, and much larger than the fibres, while the statistical approach is applied to materials containing no flaws beyond those intrinsic to the constituents. Applying either alone to hybrids presents a problem, in that they initially contain no macroscopic flaws, and would therefore require a statistical treatment of crack growth. However, the energy made available for fracture depends on the debond length (which itself varies widely with hybrid geometry) so that the macroscopic energetics of failure must also be considered.

Ideally we would wish to unify both treatments and consider the energetics of crack propagation as flaws develop during straining. In practice our approach has been determined by the lack of theoretical or experimental flaw size data so that we have been unable to adopt a crack propagation criterion for failure. Instead we consider the energy balance as a function of strain, before and after a failure in the observed mode, and arrive at a minimum strain criterion for such a failure. The observed failure strain is expected to be higher than this minimum value, because not only must the net energy balance be favourable, but also at all stages of failure, from the very first fibre break through to the ultimate propagation of a macroscopic crack, the energy conditions must be favourable. We are not at present able to discuss a full failure model incorporating the statistical aspects of flaw development, but the simpler "before and after" treatment adopted indicates that the glass plies restrict the relaxation of the carbon ply, which necessitates higher hybrid strains before sufficient energy is available for fracture. This behaviour we have termed constraint.

Consider a hybrid laminate containing a failure of the form depicted in Figure 8. At the transverse fracture the load in the carbon-ply is zero, but to either side of this position there is transfer of load by friction from the glass to carbon across the debonded interface. This results in a progressive build up of stress in the carbon-ply away from the fracture. Detailed consideration of the through-thickness displacements in the debond zone indicates a small separation at the interface, but this anticipated separation is much smaller than the observed roughness and does not counteract the frictional force, which we have assumed to be constant. The linear increase in carbon-ply load, and concomitant decrease in glass-ply load combine to a constant loading on any hybrid cross-section, Figure 14. The shear stress supported by friction is considered to be low compared with that across a bonded interface and this is shown in Figure 14 as a sharp step. The elastic load transfer rate in this bonded zone approximates to the resin shear strength, and this is shown to be much higher than the frictional stress.

The work of debonding is,

$$- 2\gamma_D dx \quad (c)$$

where γ_D is the energy to debond unit area of interface.

As the debond extends dx there is a relative displacement of glass and carbon plies of $(\epsilon_g - \epsilon_c) dx$ against the total frictional force transferred to the carbon-ply, $2\tau x$. The work of friction is,

$$- 2\tau x (\epsilon_g - \epsilon_c) dx \quad (d)$$

For the debond extension dx the hybrid extends $(\epsilon_g - \epsilon_h) dx$ and the load does work,

$$(\epsilon_g - \epsilon_h) \epsilon_h S_h dx \quad (e)$$

For static equilibrium the total energy change is zero. Therefore,

$$(a) + (b) + (c) + (d) + (e) = 0$$

and substituting (1) and (2) for ϵ_g and S_h throughout yields,

$$\frac{2\tau x^2}{\beta^2} - \frac{2\tau\epsilon_h S_c x}{\beta^2} + \frac{\epsilon_h^2 S_c^2}{2\beta^2} - 2\gamma_D = 0$$

$$\text{where } \beta = \left(\frac{1}{S_c} + \frac{1}{S_g} \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}}$$

The appropriate solution for the stable debond length L_D (Figure 8) is given by:

$$L_D = \frac{(\epsilon_h S_c - 2\beta\gamma_D^{\frac{1}{2}})}{2\tau} \quad \dots(3)$$

The physical significance of this equation can be seen from Figure 14.

The six measurable values of L_D provided by the CT - EG series of hybrids are fitted to expression (3) to obtain values for τ and γ_D . This was done by substitution of the L_D values in Table II together with the appropriate values of hybrid strain at the failure of the carbon-ply. These results are shown in Figures 15 and 16, and the values for the interface friction τ and debond energy γ_D are 0.59 MPa and 5.0 KJm⁻² respectively. The value for τ is comparatively low being only 1% of the resin shear strength (or interlaminar shear strength). This justifies the initial assumptions on frictional load transfer.

In order to estimate the strain at which the carbon-ply in the hybrid will fail we consider the energy balance before and after failure. For a small L_D the load drop at failure is negligible and the fracture is considered to proceed at constant load. As the load, and hence the strain energy of the bonded portion of hybrid, remain constant, only the volume of material contained within the debonded portion need be considered, Figure 8.

Fig. 15. Variation of the failure strain of a single carbon lamina hybrids with the stiffness parameter β .

Fig. 16. Variation of debond length with the stiffness parameter β for single carbon lamina hybrids.

The energy terms associated with tensile deformations are,

- W_1 Carbon-ply strain energy before failure
- W_2 " " " " after "
- W_3 Glass-ply " " before "
- W_4 " " " " after "
- W_5 Frictional work at debonded interface
- W_6 Transverse fracture energy
- W_7 Debonding fracture energy
- W_8 Work done by loading system.

The critical condition is that the energy change at failure should be zero, i.e.

$$(W_1 + W_3 + W_8) - (W_2 + W_4 + W_5 + W_6 + W_7) = 0 \quad \dots(4)$$

These energy terms are evaluated below for a hybrid of unit width.

The carbon strain energy density is $\frac{1}{2} \epsilon_c^2 S_c$.

$$W_1 = \epsilon_h^2 S_c L_D$$

$$W_2 = 2 \int_0^{L_D} \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_c^2 S_c dx$$

The glass strain energy density is $\frac{1}{2} \epsilon_g^2 S_g$,

$$W_3 = \epsilon_h^2 S_g L_D$$

$$W_4 = 2 \int_0^{L_D} \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_g^2 S_g dx$$

The relative movement of plies against the carbon ply load of $2\tau x$ does frictional work,

$$W_5 = 2 \int_0^{L_D} 2\tau x (\epsilon_g - \epsilon_c) dx$$

The transverse fracture energy is γ_T , so,

$$W_6 = \gamma_T t_c$$

$$W_7 = 4 \gamma_D L_D$$

The hybrid load $\epsilon_h (S_g + S_c)$ moves through a distance equal to the glass-ply extension at failure, doing work,

$$W_8 = \epsilon_h (S_g + S_c) 2 \left[\int_0^{L_D} \epsilon_g dx - (\epsilon_h L_D) \right]$$

Combining $W_1 - W_8$ in (4) while substituting $\epsilon_c = \frac{2\tau x}{S_c}$ and (1) for ϵ_g gives,

$$\epsilon_h^3 \left(\frac{S_c^3}{6 \tau \beta^2} \right) - \epsilon_h \left(\frac{2\gamma_D S_c}{\tau} \right) + \left(\frac{8}{3} \gamma_D^{\frac{3}{2}} \frac{\beta}{\tau} \right) - \gamma_T t_c = 0 \quad \dots(5)$$

γ_T has been measured at 82KJm^{-2} using the Tottersall-Tappin test configuration [9,10] and the higher positive root of (5) is plotted in Figure 17. The lower positive root of (5) corresponds to a negative debond length in (3) and has no physical meaning. Equation (5) predicts a failure-strain enhancement with increasing dispersion and decreasing carbon ratio and the experimental results for the 1-carbon lamina series show a similar trend, although the extent of the effect is much less than that predicted. The results for the thicker carbon-ply series show virtually no hybrid effect. These experimental results indicate that the constraint is only effective when the carbon-ply are very thin. The 3-carbon laminae hybrids all fail at virtually the same strain so we conclude that failure here is controlled by the intrinsic strength of the carbon. The 1-carbon lamina series shows a significant enhancement from a lower (the size effect) intrinsic failure strain of 0.0077, to 0.0155 in the hybrid.

The extent of the deviation between theory and experiment is in part explained by the crudeness of the model, which neglects shear displacements (these would be most significant for small debond lengths). Another source of error lies in the value used for γ_T . This was measured using a slow bend test which allowed full fibre pull out whereas in the hybrids there was a fast fracture with limited pull out.

5. CONCLUSIONS

(i) The present work has confirmed the existence of a hybrid effect in glass-carbon sandwich laminates. The failure strain of the carbon (brittle) layer may be enhanced to a degree dependent on laminate geometry.

Fig. 17. Carbon-ply failure strain for a range of one-, and three-carbon lamina hybrids, as found experimentally, and as predicted by the constraint model of hybrid failure. Experimental curves show only 1-carbon lamina hybrids are subject to significant constraint.

(ii) The extent of the hybrid effect is greater when the proportion of carbon is low and the dispersion is high. The carbon-ply failure strain in the hybrid can be as much as twice that of an all-carbon ply of similar thickness.

(iii) The hybrid effect is only significant when the absolute thickness of the carbon-ply is small. Virtually no effect was observed when the carbon ply thickness exceeded three laminae (0.4mm).

(iv) There is clear evidence of a size effect in all-carbon fibre laminates. Thinner laminates fail at lower strains than thicker ones over the range explored (0.13 - 2.0mm).

(v) The failure mode observed in the hybrid composites investigated was transverse fracture of the carbon ply with limited debonding along the glass-carbon ply interfaces. The extent of debonding has been shown to decrease as the dispersion is increased and the carbon proportion reduced. The analysis suggests that debonding could be inhibited if the carbon-ply could be made sufficiently thin.

(vi) Thermal stresses introduced during fabrication account for only a minor part of the observed failure strain enhancement. The bulk of the effect is attributed to a constraint mechanism but there is only moderate agreement between the experimental results and the simple model proposed.

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